

2022.05.26. Data management report

File naming and organising

During the course, we were given instructions on what a folder on our computer should look like. For the folder I selected during the course, I changed the names of the folders in the main folder, and then renamed the files to date_version_object type. This makes it easier to keep track of documents, changes to their versions, and what a file contains. After that I made a **ReadMe** file about all of the changes in the folder. In the future I will make for every experiment a ReadMe file, that contains every detail of the measurement, all of information about the evaluation, about protocols etc.

Indexing

We've set up indexing on our computer. It runs in the background and scans the contents of the hard drive. The result is a directory with file names and file contents. With this directory, I can find files especially quickly and with great search security.

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Spreadsheet Etiquette:

I choose an excel file, that contains the result of my current project. At first I used font colour or highlighting to as an explanation for myself. I made a Readme file, and put every explanation in to this test about my excel file. I had to change the rows and columns because the subjects to be as rows and variables as columns. I try to don't leave and empty cells.

Encrypt my pendrive:

I have windows 11 on my laptop. I followed all of the instructions, but my laptop did not recognize the pendrive. I tried to download bitlocker, but my laptop said, that already installed. I will try it at home.

Anonymize

In this two website we can anonymize our papers online for free.

<https://aircloak.com/top-5-free-data-anonymization-tools/>

<https://amnesia.openaire.eu/amnesia/>

Find and remove duplicate files

I downloaded the Dupeguru software, and it help to found all the files that are in double on my computer, I can assign the exact files and I can decide which one to keep and which one to delete.

Puran File recovery

I downloaded the Puran File Recovery software, and it found all the deleted files in my pendrive. After that I can assign the exact files and I can decide which one to recover and where.

Registry of research repositories:

We got acquainted with re3data.org, where we can search for different repositories with specific keywords.

Data management plan:

Data Management Plan for the submission of FOREFRONT (KKP_22) proposals

Title and identification number of the proposal	Effect of growing pressure on orbital fibroblast through activating Piezo1 receptor
Principal investigator / Host institution	Erika Galgóczi Division of Endocrinology, Department of Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary
Scheduled starting date and conclusion of the project	Starting date 2022.06.01. Due to the increase in the volume of the tissues in the orbit through endocrin orbitopathy (EOP), the orbital pressure increases, which can lead to visual impairment and, in more severe cases, blindness during the course of EOP. Investigation of the Piezo1 receptor allows the identification of an intervention site during the pathogenesis of EOP. Any agent that inhibits the main processes leading to the increase in pressure may prevent the progression of EOP
Are research data being produced during the course of the project?	Yes
Who is responsible for the management of research data? (Contact details, if not a member of the project team)	Erika Galgóczi
Please describe the type/nature of the data being produced during the course of the project.	The data will be produced during the course are different types, such as RNA, DNA samples, supernatants from cell cultures, different datasets from ELISA and PCR experiments, and meanwhile a continuous protocol management and laboratory reports will be written.

Please describe the procedure of the data collection.

The data will be collected from tools, that manage the results of the measurements in excel format.

Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored during the course of the project.

The data will be stored 3 different place, in my own laptop, one pendrive and one harddrive, and a computer in out laboratory.

Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.

The data will be stored 3 different place, in my own laptop, one pendrive and one harddrive, and a computer in out laboratory.

Please describe the accessibility of the research data.

We discuss our result in an original article.

Which research data of the project will be of open access?

The original article will be open access.

Is there any reason or necessity to restrict the accessibility of the research data?

Yes, because it is quite a new field in this topic, and we have competitors.

Do you use any standard metadata? (DublinCore, Datacite, etc.)

not yet

Please describe where and how the metadata will be stored during the course of the project.

The metadata will be stored in our laboratory computer.

Please describe how the metadata will be accessible?

The metadata will be stored on the internet, e.g. Zenodo, where it has own DOI.

Do you use standard or unique identifiers? (DOI, ORCID)

Yes, I have ORCID.

Please describe where and how the metadata, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.

Zenodo

Does the handling of research data comply with the GDPR regulations?

no